

THE EFFECT OF OXYGEN PLASMA TREATMENT ON THE SURFACE ENERGY OF EXFOLIATED GRAPHITE AND THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPHITE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Wetting of composite filler by a polymer matrix is essential to obtaining adhesion and optimal composite performance. The ability to probe the surface for chemical functionality and acid-base interactions is valuable for matching fillers with the appropriate matrix. In this study, the surface energy of exfoliated graphite nanoparticles was determined via wicking measurements using water at varied pH followed by analysis using the Washburn equation. The surface energy provided the basis for determining the work of adhesion and the dispersive and acid-base interactions. This wicking process was also applied in order to evaluate chemistry changes induced on the surface of exfoliated graphite by an oxygen-plasma treatment. The work of adhesion has its highest value at larger values of pH as a result of the acidic functional groups added to the exfoliated graphite by oxygen-plasma treatment. Analysis of XPS data indicates that the primary functionality added to the surface comes from hydroxyl groups. However, carbonyl and carboxyl groups are also present. The effect of the time between oxygen plasma treatment and surface chemical condition was also studied in this research. It was determined that the work of adhesion decreases with time when the oxygen plasma treated graphite is stored in air. After 24 hours the work of adhesion stabilized over the period in which it was evaluated. The decrease in work of adhesion reflects chemical changes that occurred with storage in air. XPS analysis shows that there is an increase of 140% carbonyl functionality and a 22.4% decrease in hydroxyl functionality associated with these temporal changes. Since carbonyl groups are less reactive with basic solutions than hydroxyl groups, the work of adhesion was lowered. Surface chemical changes were correlated to mechanical properties of composites made with oxygen plasma treated graphite reinforcement.

INTRODUCTION

The interface between composite filler and polymer matrix has long been established as a critical component of composite success or failure. Inadequate wetting leads to poor adhesion and subsequently poor mechanical properties. Recently increasing research activity with nano-scale fillers increases the importance on interfacial adhesion when nano-scale reinforcements are utilized which have incredibly high surface areas. One such nano-scale filler that is being explored in our group at Michigan State University is exfoliated graphite. Graphite is a naturally occurring, layered, crystal, which can be intercalated with sulfuric and nitric acids, heated rapidly and ground by ultrasonic mixing to platelets 15 micron in diameter and 20 nanometer thickness¹. Results using exfoliated graphite particles as reinforcement have been published as mechanical and thermal reinforcements in polystyrene^{2,3}, and electrical and mechanical reinforcements in epoxy⁴. The interface between these materials has not been extensively studied, though published results indicate that oxygen plasma treatment increases the strength of a graphite epoxy nanocomposites⁵. There has been much published research about surface modifications, which improve the adhesion properties of carbon fibers^{6,7} and more recently, carbon nanotubes⁸. Once modified, one common method of surface analysis of these materials is wettability obtained by the work of adhesion (W_A), which is related to the contact angle through Young's equation.

$$(1) \quad W_A = \gamma_l(1 + \cos \theta)$$

According to Fowkes contributions, the work of adhesion can be described at the sum of dispersive forces and acid-base forces⁹:

$$(2) \quad W_A = W^D + W^{AB}$$

The London dispersive forces comprise W^D and can be calculated from the dispersive component of the probe liquid and sample substrate.

$$(3) \quad W^D = 2(\gamma_l^D * \gamma_s^D)^{0.5}$$

The acid-base component of the work of adhesion arises from chemical reaction between functional groups on the substrate and the chemical functionality of the probe liquid.

$$(4) \quad W^{AB} = -\sum f_i n_i^{AB} \Delta H_i^{AB}$$

In this case, f is a conversion factor, n is the number of reactive sites, and ΔH is the heat of reaction to form these surface complexes. So, once the contact angle is known, it provides a wealth of insight into the acid-base nature of the substrate. Wicking techniques have previously been developed that utilize the Washburn equation for obtaining the contact angle of powdered substrates¹⁰. The Washburn equation is

$$(5) \quad \cos \theta = \left(\frac{m^2}{t} \right) * \frac{\eta}{\gamma \rho^2 c}$$

where m^2/t is obtained from experimental data, c is the material constant (or capillary constant), and η , γ , ρ are the viscosity, surface energy and density of the probe liquid. The material constant is obtained by using a low energy liquid, such as hexane, where the contact angle is zero. The left hand side of (5) reduces to one and the equation can be solved for c . This technique has been used for many different

particulate materials, but has never been applied to exfoliated graphite nanoparticles. It is the focus of this study to apply the Washburn wicking technique to exfoliated graphite and determine the acid-base nature of the surface. XPS analysis will be used to compliment the wicking results. Once a reliable characterization technique is established, an emphasis will be made on using plasma treatment to chemically modify the platelet functionality and improve wettability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Exfoliated Graphite

The exfoliated graphite used for this study was UCAR 160-50A. It is graphite intercalated with sulfuric and nitric acid at a four to one ratio. The graphite was heated in a furnace at 900 °C for five minutes, then mixed in acetone with ultrasonic mixing for two hours. At the end of this process the average particle diameter is 15 μm .

Washburn Wicking

Washburn wicking of exfoliated graphite was conducted on via a Cahn microbalance. PTFE capillary tubes with a 0.0625" diameter were filled with 20 mg of graphite material. The graphite was compressed by a UTS apparatus to a compressive force of five pounds (1630 psi, see Fig 1). The capillary was suspended from the microbalance and immersed in the probe liquid for the wicking procedure. Half of the capillaries were suspended in hexane for three minutes, then dried at 50 °C for four hours *in vacuo* and reused for an aqueous probe liquid. Wicking with aqueous solutions was conducted for five minutes and seven repetitions were conducted at each pH increment. Capillaries were discarded after their first use in aqueous solution.

Figure 1: Schematic of sample capillary during compression.

Aqueous probe liquid preparation was conducted with deionized water (DI) and either hydrochloric acid (HCl) or sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to decrease or increase the pH. At pH 6, DI water was used with no modification. For each pH increment, the pH was tested daily before and after each test. In cases where the final pH was 0.25 more or less than the original pH, the data was not processed and the experiment was repeated with fresh probe liquid. For nominal pH values of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12, the actual pH was within 0.1 of the nominal value. For nominal value 14, the actual value 13.7-13.8. Small ion additions of HCl and NaOH do not affect the viscosity, surface energy or density of water.

XPS

The carbon 1s spectral envelope was fit using an asymmetric Gaussian-Lorentzian mix for the main graphitic peak (fit to 284.6 eV). Additional peaks were fit using a model of approximately 1.5 eV shift per bond to oxygen. Oxygen 1s spectral envelopes were fit with two peaks, one at approximately 533 eV assigned to hydroxyl groups and one at approximately 531 eV assigned as oxygen bound to two carbons (ether, carbonyl).

Oxygen Plasma Treatment

The exfoliated graphite material was placed on a flat aluminum foil surface and covered with stainless steel mesh to prevent volatilization during vacuum pumping and venting. The pressure inside the plasma chamber was reduced to 0.050 tor before the material was treated for 2 minutes at 225 W. Following treatment the sample was placed in a sample vial and sealed until testing was conducted. No precautions were taken to modify the headspace of the vial from atmospheric conditions. In the case of time effect studies, the sample vial was left open to the atmosphere for the indicated time period. Humidity treated material was placed in a humidity chamber after 24 hours in air and exposed to 24 hours of 80% relative humidity (RH) and 80 °C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XPS

It is clear from XPS results that surface chemistry changes are induced by oxygen plasma treatment (see Table 1). The untreated graphite surface has an oxygen to carbon elemental ratio of 0.024, while after two minutes of oxygen plasma treatment, this increases this to 0.040. The functional groups change form too. The untreated graphite has only C-O-C or C-OH functionality. The plasma treated material not only has a drastic increase in C-OH and C-O-C functionality, but also contains carboxyl and carbonyl groups. It is also clear from XPS results that the surface chemistry is dynamic with time exposure to air, most probably due to interaction with atmospheric moisture. Though the oxygen to carbon ratio is relatively constant with time, the functionality changes. The decrease in hydroxyl functionality is clear, as is the increase in carbonyl functionality. Carbonyl functionality increases by 140% and hydroxyl functionality decreases by 22.4%.

Table 1: XPS Results Indicating The Exfoliated Graphite Surface Chemistry Before Plasma Treatment, After Treatment and the Effect of Air Exposure.

t=	Untreated	0 hrs		24 hrs		48 hrs		24 h + 24 h humidity	
O/C ratio	0.022	0.040		0.057		0.050		0.053	
		Rel Conc.	% Change	Rel Conc.	% Change	Rel Conc.	% Change	Rel Conc.	% Change
C-no oxygen	92.6%	80.3%	---	75.8%	-5.6%	79.2%	-1.3%	80.3%	-0.1%
Hydroxyl or Ether	4.3%	10.6%	---	9.8%	-7.6%	8.2%	-22.4%	6.0%	-43.7%
Carbonyl	---	1.0%	---	3.3%	228.5%	2.4%	140.1%	2.9%	189.7%
Carboxyl	---	2.3%	---	2.8%	23.0%	2.8%	26.4%	2.7%	18.9%

Washburn Wicking Results

Reproducible packing is essential to successful wicking because the Washburn equation is very sensitive to changes in capillary constant and must be very accurate for reliable results. The load cell compression procedure was developed to ensure reproducible packing. Figure 2 gives a representative appearance of exfoliated graphite packing curve and it should be noted that the near infinite slope at 5 lbs of force is reproducible for all samples. The reproducibility of the force curve indeed points to reproducible packing, as there was less than 10% error in the value of the material constant.

Figure 2: Plot of capillary compressive force vs. compressive displacement.

With the material constant established, aqueous solutions at varied pH were used to obtain W_A through use of the Washburn equation. Figure 3 shows a comparative plot for untreated exfoliated

Figure 3: Plot of wicking results for untreated and plasma treated exfoliated graphite indicating the increased acidic functionality that comes from plasma treatment.

Figure 4: Plot showing how the work of adhesion decreases with exposure of oxygen plasma treated graphite to air.

graphite and oxygen plasma treated graphite. At high pH, the oxygen plasma treated graphite has a higher work of adhesion, indicating that the surface was oxidized by the plasma treatment and acid groups were introduced onto the surface. This is consistent with XPS results that indicate increased hydroxyl and carboxyl groups on the surface.

The wicking study also senses surface chemistry changes in oxygen plasma treated graphite in air. Figure 4 is a plot of W_A changes with time obtained at pH 14. It is clear from the plot that the functional groups introduced on the surface change with time exposure in air. The wicking results, confirm XPS results that indicate primary functionality is changing from hydroxyl to carbonyl functionality. Hydroxyl groups have a stronger acidic nature and would react more strongly at pH 14 than carbonyl groups. So, as the concentration of hydroxyl groups decrease and the concentration of carbonyl groups increase, the work of adhesion decreases.

As stated earlier, this oxygen plasma treatment has been shown to improve the mechanical properties of exfoliated graphite epoxy nanocomposites¹¹. At three volume percent, the flexural strength was improved by greater than 10%. Because oxygen plasma introduces more functional groups on the surface of the platelets, better wetting is achieved and the mechanical properties are improved.

CONCLUSIONS

A Washburn wicking study is an effective way to characterize the acid-base nature of exfoliated graphite surfaces. UTS compression packing provides a reproducible packing procedure and reliable sample preparation. XPS also serves to compliment and confirm the wicking results. Oxygen plasma is an effective method for increasing acid functionality of exfoliated graphite, but must be processed immediately to avoid surface chemistry changes in air.

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